

Scaling Up Secure Processing, Anonymization And Generation Of Health Data For EU Cross Border Collaborative Research And Innovation

Project Overview

In SECURED, we offer a one stop collaboration hub, the SECURED Innohub, that can provide a secure environment for decentralized, cooperative processing of health data through SMPC techniques as well as generation of new, synthetic data and anonymization tools to health data providers and users.

Our goal is to facilitate the broad adoption of health datasets across Europe by making the interconnection between EU health data hubs, the health data analytics research community, health application innovators, and end users.

The SECURED vision is to kick start an EU cross-border health data collaboration ecosystem for data providers, data researchers and innovators that will be able to produce new AI based data analytics solutions and stem innovation.

Project Objectives

- Develop scalable Secure Multiparty Computation (SMPC) schemes for AI-based health data analytics tools.
- Provide advanced Anonymization on Health datasets and AI models.
- Provide adaptable, configurable, and versatile Synthetic-data-generation tools and services for health/medical synthetic data.
- Offer scalability support for SECURED health-data-related services and tools through the SECURED Federation Infrastructure.
- Integrate SECURED components in the SECURED Innohub that can offer tools, services, training and knowledge for a broad range of researchers and users.
- Evaluate the SECURED solution in terms of legal and ethical aspects, regarding cross-border use of anonymized and synthetic datasets, and AI models.
- Validation and Demonstration with four use cases involving cross-border EU health data hubs.
- Provide a viable dissemination, exploitation and business model of the SECURED solution.

Open Call

- The Open Call is designed to involve external third parties employing AI solutions in line with SECURED's objectives.
- We welcome proposals from individuals, organizations, and groups who are passionate about making a positive impact in reliable and unbiased AI and data analytics in the healthcare industry.
- Proposals will be evaluated based on their creativity, feasibility, impact, and alignment with our organization's mission.

Timeline

- **Call for proposals launch:** 1/8/2024
- **Proposal submission deadline:** 31/10/2024, 17:00 CET
- **Notification of selected projects:** 30/11/2024
- **Project implementation period:** 1/12/2024-1/5/2025
- **Completion of works:** 1/5/2025

Funding

- **Total allocated budget:** 150,000 euros
- **Maximum funding per project:** 26,000 euros
+1,500 euros for travel costs to the final event

Full announcement: secured-project.eu/secured_open_call

Contact us: secured-open-call@list.uva.nl

Stay updated: Subscribe to our mailing list: shorturl.at/Wz3ly

Consortium

Project info

Start: 01.01.2023

Duration: 36 months

Participating Organisations: 17

Number of countries: 9

Project acronym: SECURED

Call: HORIZON-HLTH-2022-IND-13

Topic: HORIZON-HLTH-2022-IND-13-02

Type of action: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions

EU Contribution: € 6,999,723.25

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